

Topic: CIRC BIO-01-01 Circular Cities and Regions Initiative's project development assistance (CCRI-PDA)

D2.1 Stakeholders' engagement strategy

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D2.1 Stakeholders' engagement strategy

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Abstract	This deliverable describes the established engagement strategy of the multisectoral and multidisciplinary stakeholders that will be used for engagement in the activities of WP1, WP3 and WP4 of DECISO. This deliverable has been produced within "T2.1 – Prepare, form and nurse the four Circular Economy Ecosystems in the pilots". This task is connected to the activities of WP1, WP3 and WP4, aiming to promote active stakeholders' participation and involvement and a commitment to the circular economy issues identified by each pilot.
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Explain Deliverable Dependency/ Connection	"D6.3 – Informed Consent procedures" details the informed consent to be used within the activities related to the stakeholders' engagement.
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1. Objective and Purpose

The objective of the DECISO project is to foster the interest of potential investors and to create a favourable climate for the development of the Circular Economy (CE).

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The purpose of DECISO project is to accompany and assist promoters with actions for mobilising stakeholders to promote systemic solutions that involve all actors of the value chain of an asset, and also, all those who can influence, even indirectly, the value and the emergence of Ecosystems of CE.

The deliverable “D2.1-Stakeholders’ engagement strategy” describes the established engagement strategy of the multi-sectoral and multidisciplinary stakeholders that will engage stakeholders in the activities of WP1, WP3 and WP4. This deliverable is produced within the “T2.1 – Prepare, form and nurse the four Circular Economy Ecosystems in the pilots”. The strategy aims to promote the active stakeholders’ participation and involvement and a commitment to the circular economy issues identified by each pilot of the DECISO project. The idea is to provide the DECISO project’s partners with guidelines for stakeholders’ engagement, which can then be adapted according to the needs at different scales (from the local to the European level).

Planning and implementing CESolutions requires engagement and collaboration among different stakeholders, i.e. groups or individuals that can affect or be affected by the activities of the organisations in DECISO (Freeman, 1984).

The DECISO stakeholders’ engagement process will consist of the steps depicted in the following figure:

Figure 1: Process of engagement

The steps are detailed in the following sections.

2. Subject and Key objectives of the engagement

Aiming to foster the interest of potential investors and create a favourable climate for the development of CE projects, DECISO will accompany the actions for assisting promoters with actions for mobilising stakeholders to promote systemic solutions that involve all actors of the value chain of an asset and, all those who can influence, even indirectly, the value and the emergence of Ecosystems of CE.

The DECISO project assumes that the stakeholders' engagement process is voluntary. According to APGA guidelines, [APGA Guideline for stakeholder engagement, 2015, stakeholder-engagement-guidelines.pdf (apga.org.au)], "Stakeholder engagement is an ongoing process that builds relationships between parties, fostering respect, enabling information exchange and achieving mutually acceptable outcomes". These guidelines also suggest that an effective stakeholders engagement process needs to:

- providing information;
- capacity building to equip communities and stakeholders to effectively engage;
- listening and responding to community and stakeholder concerns;
- including communities and stakeholders in relevant decision-making processes;
- developing good will and an understanding of objectives and priorities which will lead to confidence in decisions;
- establishing a realistic understanding of potential outcomes; and
- building an understanding of the decision-making process".

3. Stakeholders' identification and selection process

The multiple interests, the potential impacts (social, economic, environmental, political), and the interests of the research and academic world related to the CE require engaging and mobilising different types of stakeholders (multi-sectoral and multidisciplinary) due to:

- involve all the actors of the value chain for defining everyone's roles and commitments;
- create the ground developing a shared understanding of issues and objectives to co-create a commonly agreed and shared vision and action plan;
- connect/exchange the pilot experience with European CE projects, communities and CCRI (Circular Cities and Regions Initiative);
- increase the awareness of stakeholders on the good practices that can be applied in each piloting area based on the set objectives and the ambition of the programme;
- identify the financial supports available at local, national and European levels, 6) identify the framework legislative/regulatory necessary for the success of the programme.

There are many stakeholders' classifications in the literature, and many different classifications are also usually adopted by the partners of DECISO. The Grant Agreement indicated the need to engage producers, processors, retailers, CE networks, service providers, consumers as citizens, governmental institutions, NGOs and industry. Table 1 describes the different classifications the DECISO partners used at the project beginning.

A new classification has been defined considering the different experiences in a process of harmonisation of the different classifications. Each type of stakeholder is described considering their value-based motivations, expectancies, role, level of engagement and scale (from the local stakeholders to the national and European), i.e., the parameters. Before providing the table of stakeholders' clusters, a description of the parameters is given.

Table 1: Stakeholders' classification generally used by the DECISO partners (this table has to be filled in by each partner, and harmonised by CNR in one table only)

DECISO partner	Stakeholders' classification before the DECISO project starting
CNR	Policymakers, Civil Society, Industry / (waste management, agriculture ...), Universities and research centres, Investors, Private sector consulting companies (Consultancy)
CCDRA	National, regional and local authorities and agencies, public networks and companies, universities and research centres, private sector/industries and civil society
IRRADIARE	National, regional and local authorities and agencies, public networks and companies, universities and research centres, private sector/industries and civil society
MDHA	Policymakers, construction/waste management industry, Universities - research centres
PDM	Policymakers, Civil Society, Industry/waste management - agriculture, Universities - research centres – spin-off, Private sector consulting companies
FHH	Policymakers, Administration, Private Sector, Science
OOWV	Policymakers, Civil Society, Industry/agriculture, Universities and research centres, Investors
OV	Citizens, Civil Society, Public Administrations, Agencies, Industries/developers, Industries/services, Consultancy, Investors
ACR+	Local and regional authorities, public authority networks, national authorities or agencies, NGOs, Academia, Social Utility Companies, Private Partners, Consultancies, Professional Federations
KOYS	Citizens, Civil Society, Public Administrations, Agencies, Industries/developers, Industries/services, Consultancy, Policymakers, Research Centres, Academia, Investors

The Stakeholders' Value-based motivations return us information on what is important and what are the stakeholder priorities. It is also essential to understand the stakeholders' expectations of the project outcomes and the Role of each stakeholder, i.e., what she or he can do. The role is related to the level of engagement. The description of the potential levels of engagement is given below in accordance with (AccountAbility, 2015):

- Remain passive: No active communication is required, and the engagement is mainly based on letters, the media, and websites.
- Monitor: One-way communication (from the stakeholder to the organisation) takes place through the media and internet tracking, and second-hand reports from other stakeholders, possibly via targeted interviews, are included in this category.
- Advocate: One-way communication (from the organisation to the stakeholder) occurs via pressure on regulatory bodies, lobbying efforts, and other advocacy efforts through social media.
- Inform: One-way communication (from the organisation to the stakeholder) takes place through bulletins and letters, brochures, reports and websites, speeches, conferences, and public presentations
- Transact: Limited two-way engagement takes place through public–private partnerships, private finance initiatives, grant provisions, and cause-related marketing.
- Consult: Limited two-way engagement takes place, wherein the organisation asks questions and the stakeholders answer them. This approach is based on surveys, focus groups, meetings with selected stakeholders, public meetings, and workshops.
- Negotiate: Limited two-way engagement occurs for discussions on a specific issue or a range of issues, the goal being to reach a consensus. This engagement mainly involves collective bargaining with workers through their trade unions.
- Involve: Two-way or multi-way engagement occurs, involving learning on all sides, but the stakeholders and organisation act independently through multi-stakeholder forums, advisory panels, consensus-building processes, focus groups, and online engagement tools.

- Collaborate: Two-way or multi-way engagement takes place leading to joint learning and decision-making through joint projects, joint ventures, partnerships, multi-stakeholder initiatives, and online collaborative platforms; and
- Empower: Stakeholders play a relevant role in shaping organisational agendas; thus, their engagement is a key aspect of the firm's governance, strategy, and operations.

Finally, DECISO can engage stakeholders from the local to the national and European levels. Indeed, the processes, practices and lessons learned in the pilot areas must be shared with other areas and contexts.

Table 2 summarises the stakeholders' classification adopted in DECISO and the description of Value-Based motivations, the Expectancies from the project outcomes, the Role that the stakeholder can play, the level of engagement, and the scale. The classes of stakeholders that need to be engaged within DECISO are Citizens, Civil Society, Policymakers, Public Administrations and Agencies, the Private sector and industry (consultancy, developers, services), Academia/Research Centres and Spin-offs, and Investors.

Table 2: Value-based motivations, expectancies and roles related to the engagement of the different types of stakeholders

TYPE OF STAKEHOLDER	VALUE-BASED MOTIVATIONS (What is important and what are the priorities for the stakeholder?)	EXPECTANCIES FROM THE PROJECT OUTCOMES	ROLE THAT THE STAKEHOLDER CAN PLAY (What is the role the stakeholder can play?)	LEVEL OF ENGAGEMENT	SCALE
Citizens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness about how to implement CE practices at the household level. • Know more and better the population's needs and habits. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engaged in awareness campaigns and training courses and practices. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spread-by-mouth and by-social the relevance of each solution in pilots. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involve 	Mainly Local
Civil Society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitating systemic societal change towards the CE • Building a sustainable perspective at the local (city/region), national and EU levels. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promoting sustainability and wellbeing • Sharing and discussing Knowledge related to CE and its adoption to improve the quality of life. • Stakeholder engagement activities to discuss and share the knowledge base on good practices, and a plan as a result of a consultation and collaboration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating a common awareness of CE and its impact on the quality of life and wellbeing. • Sharing Knowledge. • Contribute to the communities' health and promote sustainability and well-being. • Involve and engage the citizens at the local level. <p>Provide information within the local boundaries.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inform • Consult • Involve • Collaborate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local • Nation • European

		with other stakeholders.			
Policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Focusing more on CE than in the past, and working towards a systemic societal shift for more CE Identification of scalable, sustainable CE city/regional solutions (with a view on the specific topic of each area) Facilitating systemic societal change towards the CE (with a view on the specific topic of each area) <p>Promote CE in the city and in the area strengthening CE efforts in compliance with city/regional, national and EU strategies.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding how CE can be promoted. Engagement activities to discuss and share a plan that is the result of a consultation and collaboration with other stakeholders. Sharing a strategy for implementing CE solutions Identifying the operative steps to be taken to facilitate change and shift the focus towards CE. <p>Stakeholder engagement activities to discuss and share a plan that is the result of a consultation and collaboration with other stakeholders.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide instruments to ensure long-term sustainability (regulatory tools, and incentives). Increasing activity, competitiveness, and welfare through the CE (at different scales). Compliance CE actions with city/regional strategies. Implementation of the CE (with a view to the specific topic) in accordance with national and EU government Create incentives for shifting towards more CE. Give insights on what is asked from civil society. Give Insights on decision-making processes. <p>Exploitation and upscaling of pilots.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inform Involve Collaborate Empower 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local Nation European
Public Administrations and Agencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implement good practices on CE, in the different sectors (for example, waste management and pollution reduction) in accordance with existing measures. Ensure compliance with national and EU-level regulations. <p>Create incentives to promote CE.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enrich the knowledge base on good practices. Discuss new business and sustainability models. Develop a scheme that encloses operative steps. Introduce financial schemes for developing CE. Pave the way towards implementation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide insights into the structural framework. Provide data for sustainability models evaluation. Develop incentives. Define the calls. Evaluating the feasibility of possible CE approaches Assessment of operative steps proposed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inform Consult Involve Collaborate Empower 	Local

		of CE approaches. Create a favourable climate for CE projects.	Sharing experiences and Knowledge on the implementation process.		
Private sector and industry (consultancy, developers, services)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support the transition to more circularity in the economy bringing the CE to the core logic of business as promoting competitiveness in the medium term (in accordance with the economic, environmental, and social sustainability) Facilitating sustainable value creation finding ways to conciliate sustainability and economy. Know about people's habits and solutions needs. Compliance with the European and national policies promoting sustainability and CE.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder engagement activities to discuss and share a plan that is the result of a consultation and collaboration with other stakeholders. New Business model that facilitates sustainability and produces revenue. Creation of a financial template for improving circularity. Availability of more CE projects due to funding options Promote investment into CE solutions. Tested scenarios and solutions. Recommendation on feasibility and economic features for implementing the new business model and further improvements.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide feedback on the feasibility of solutions for CE and the proposed frameworks. Identify new business opportunities. Feeds from the market. Provide an update on the framework related to the specific sector. Private sector and consultancy. Increase networking, and of the proposed frameworks with sister projects. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inform Consult Involve Collaborate Empower 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local Nation European
Academia Research Centres Spin-offs /	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Providing and sharing Knowledge and tools related to CE, the use, usability and perceptions of its solutions, and the implementation Promoting and creating innovations (Social, technological, etc.) aiming to strengthen CE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitating systemic societal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New Knowledge for CE New tools for supporting knowledge sharing and services on CE. Stakeholder engagement activities to discuss and share a plan that is the result of a consultation and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share Knowledge. Provide scientific progress to unsolved issues. Producing innovations, and innovative tools and developing new business models. Increase the performance of solutions and procedures for CE. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inform Involve Collaborate Empower 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local National European

	<p>change towards the CE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Proposing solutions on how to make CE an integral part of society. o Creating sustainable and climate-friendly solutions 	<p>collaboration with other stakeholders.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New approaches and Business model on CE that facilitate sustainability and produces revenue. 			
Investors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • - open new profitable investment opportunities and economic growth in sectors with high environmental impact but with high circularity potential; • - meet growing consumer demand for the circular economy and products that combat climate change and the loss of biodiversity and improve health conditions; • - meet the changes in regulations that governments and society are implementing to combat climate change, pollution and the loss of biodiversity; 	<p>Report of costs effectiveness and potential revenue.</p> <p>Increase public private cooperation in CE projects design and implementation.</p>	<p>Planning and providing financial support for the industrialisation of CE solutions, and for transfer to other ecosystems.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inform • Consult • Involve • Collaborate • Empower • 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local, • National • European
Media	<p>Collecting news to be shared</p>	<p>Collect information on CE solutions and financial schemes defined</p>	<p>Disseminate information on CE solutions and financial scheme</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local • National • European

– **Citizens (General public):** they are “ordinary people, especially all the people who are not members of a particular organisation or who do not have any special type of knowledge” (Oxford dictionary last access 08/02/2023, <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/general-public>) and their engagement is important for understanding their needs and awareness with respect to the importance and the potential impacts of the CE within society and understanding their expectations behaviours. Their engagement is particularly significant as the entire society has to accept and cooperate for any change that promotes CE.

The project will engage them in the collective awareness campaign and training courses sharing good practices. This strategy is expected to produce a snowball effect by spreading by mouth and social media the relevance of each solution in pilots.

- Civil society: i.e. “actors and institutional forms such as registered charities, development nongovernmental organisations, community groups, women's organisations, faith-based organisations, professional associations, trade unions, self-help groups, social movements, business associations, coalitions and advocacy groups” (WHO, 2007) should be engaged based on their interest in facilitating systemic societal change towards the CE, and in building a sustainable perspective (at different scales, from the territorial one, mainly in the pilot areas, to the national and EU level). In particular, CE orienting the reuse of products implies a deep awareness, acceptance and adoption of the new model requiring that each one plays both, the role of the consumer and supplier. Civil society can contribute to sharing Knowledge, providing information and engaging citizens already at the local level to build a common awareness of CE and its impact on well-being and quality of life.
- Policymakers: a policymaker is defined (Cambridge Dictionary, last access 08/02/2023, <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/policymaker>) as a member of a government department, legislature, or other organisations which are responsible for making new rules, laws, etc... This group includes policymakers at local, national, and European levels. Policymakers' engagement can be motivated by the need to encourage and facilitate any societal change for the adoption of circular economy and reinforcing CE efforts in compliance with city/regional, national and EU strategies, and motivated by the need to identify a scalable, sustainable CE city/regional solutions (with a view on the specific topic of each area). DECISO will engage policymakers aiming to understand how CE can be promoted, to discuss and share a plan that is the result of a consultation and collaboration with other stakeholders, to discuss and share a strategy for implementing CE solutions, to identify the operative steps for activating the transition toward CE, to engage all stakeholders to discuss and share a plan that is the result of a consultation and collaboration with other stakeholders. Policymakers should encourage civil society behaviours to promote the implementation and the transition toward the CE. In this context, policymakers can introduce specific measures (e.g., subsidies, incentives, tax breaks, and funding start-up ideas) to support innovative solutions. Their engagement will be significant for following dialogue and a process of common understanding, co-building, and sharing the outcomes of the DECISO project from the pilots. In particular, policymakers for the four pilots will provide instruments to ensure long-term sustainability (regulatory tools and incentives), the compliancy of actions with city/regional CE strategies, and the improvement of competitiveness and welfare through the CE. Policymakers will give insights on what is asked from civil society and insights on decision-making processes in a continuous mutual understanding. Policymakers at different scales will promote the exploitation and upscaling of the pilots.
- Public Administrations and Agencies: they should be engaged, as they have in charge of the implementation of guidelines and good practices for CE related to the different topics (waste management, rainwater management, etc.), also promoting CE with incentives and checking for the compatibility with regulations and laws at the different scales. They are the actors that (based on the new CE business and sustainability models, and the discussed operative steps and the financial schemes for CE) will give a picture of the structural framework and data for sustainability model evaluation. They operatively define incentive tools and calls and assess the steps performed. Finally, they should share their experiences and Knowledge related to the entire process implemented.
- Private sector and industry (consultancy, developers, services): the private sector consists of the "businesses and industries that are not owned or controlled by the government" (Cambridge Dictionary last

accessed 08/02/2023, <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/private-sector>), and includes industry (with developers and services) as well as consultancies. The engagement of the private sector and industry in different sectors related to the topics of the four pilots of the DECISO project (such as waste management, rainwater, agriculture, construction,...) may produce specific positive effects, as in the perspective of CE, they can play both, the roles of consumers, as well as the role of suppliers, representing key actors of innovative business models. Their active engagement is crucial for any transformation from a linear to a circular business model. Thus, the engagement of industries should be based on sharing their goals and their choice to adopt a CE business model. In particular, the private sector and industry could consider supporting the transition to more circularity in the economy bringing the CE to the core logic of business as promoting competitiveness in the medium term (in accordance with the economic, environmental, and social sustainability), and facilitating value creation finding ways to conciliate sustainability and economy, also based on the people's habits and solutions need, and in compliance with the European and national policies promoting sustainability and CE. DECISO can engage the private sector and industry within activities to discuss and share a plan that is the result of a consultation and collaboration with other stakeholders, can propose a new business model that facilitates sustainability, produces revenue, proposes tested scenarios and solutions, and recommendation for further improvements. DECISO will create financial templates to improve circularity; this will improve the availability of funding options for CE projects and will stimulate investments into CE.

The private sector and industries will provide feedback on the feasibility of solutions for CE and the proposed frameworks and will identify new business opportunities (feeds from the market, update on the framework related to the specific sector). Private sector consultancy can contribute to increasing networking, and sharing experiences and the proposed frameworks with sister projects.

– Academia / Research Centres, Spin-offs: academia is defined as “the life, community, or world of teachers, schools, and education” (Webster dictionary, last access 8/02/2023, <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/academia>) and, it mainly refers to universities. It carries out research activities together with other public and private research and innovation institutions (such as research centres and spin-offs). They usually work to provide and share Knowledge and tools related to CE, the use, usability and perceptions of the proposed solutions, and their implementation. They are also motivated by promoting and creating innovations (Social, technological, etc.) aiming to strengthen CE. This is done by proposing solutions on how to make CE an integral part of society and facilitating systemic societal change towards the CE. DECISO will produce new Knowledge, will identify new tools, will organise stakeholder engagement activities to discuss and share a plan that is the result of a consultation and collaboration, and produce new approaches and a Business model on CE that facilitates sustainability and will produce revenue. Academia / Research Centres, Spin-offs should contribute to sharing Knowledge, to the scientific progresses for unsolved issues, to innovative tools and new business models, and increasing performances of solutions and procedures identified.

– Investors: Investors are defined as "natural persons (citizens) [and permanent residents] of a Contracting Party and enterprises organised in accordance with the law of a Contracting Party [that seeks to make, are making, or have made an investment]" (OECD, last access 8/02/2023, <https://www.oecd.org/daf/mai/pdf/dg2/dg2961e.pdf>).

Defining new financing CE models implies the strong participation of all types of stakeholders. Indeed, CE funding models imply overcoming the linear business, and can produce the optimisation in terms of resources efficiency, adopting circular practices and contributing to the sustainability goals by opening new profitable investments opportunities.

DECISO proposal already identified some funding in each pilot. The project aims to engage public and private investors.

The Saarinen & Aarikka-Stenroos's [Saarinen & Aarikka-Stenroos's, 2023] study underlines that a transition toward a CE requires financing coming from the private sector as well as from the public sector with financial incentives, funding, financial instruments de-risking investments for the private sector, policies, etc. and acting as an example to the private sector.

But currently CE does not attract sufficiently funding, and "financing CE activities is significantly more difficult for SMEs than for large" [Saarinen & Aarikka-Stenroos's, 2023]

Private investors, when evaluating whether to make an investment, will take into account the risks and potential revenues. However, a factor that could influence private investors to move towards the CE is the positive orientation of consumers towards the CE products, as well as tax incentives.

For this reason, the collaboration of public and private investors, and the dialogue with Civil Society is crucial to create a trustful ecosystem, as it enables to *know more on perceptions of CE solutions from the different actors*.

Investors collaborating with DECISO can obtain the picture of *costs effectiveness and potential revenue* from CE in the different areas and the different sectors. Based on this dialogue, the role of investor should be related to *planning and providing financial support for the industrialisation of CE solutions, and for transfer to other ecosystems*.

The investors' engagement is relevant as it facilitates the adoption of the CE making it evident to the industries and companies in general, as well as to society that sustainability and competitiveness are the values that will produce advantages in the medium and long term, also for competitive positioning. Investors can contribute to DECISO planning and providing financial support for the industrialisation of CE solutions, and for transferring solutions to other ecosystems.

The advantages of engaging the identified stakeholders' categories by developing a collaborative network are evident through access to Knowledge, producing a competitive advantage in terms of innovative ideas. Many of the stakeholders can be identified among the partners of sister projects, the CCRI community members and stakeholders in the countries and pilot areas. Building a DECISO community with a stakeholders' feeling of belongingness is a crucial point. Each partner can start to send an invitation letter (Appendix I) to stakeholders jointly with the informed consent to sign (defined and shared in advance with partners, and included in the deliverable "D6.3 – Informed Consent procedures").

500 local stakeholders (of the types identified), 20 stakeholders at the national and EU level, and about 40 organizations supporting the development of the financial schemes will be engaged and included in the community and the database.

– **Media:** Media refers to organisations that play a key role "of communication which have functions such as informing, raising awareness, education, socialization, entertainment and agenda setting, including all kinds of oral, written and visual images." (IGI Global "The Understanding of Entertainment in Press Enterprises in Turkey", last access 8/02/2023, <https://www.igi-global.com/chapter/the-understanding-of-entertainment-in-press-enterprises-in-turkey/113544>).

The DECISO stakeholders' identification and selection process foresee:

1. to collect information and establish a contact with the sister projects, (EU projects, National and local projects),
2. to identify and select the stakeholders, different per type, value-based motivations, expectancies with respect to the objectives of the engagement,
3. participating in the CCDRI community activities and engaging them in the DECISO activities.

Once identified the types of stakeholders, the value-based motivations, and their expectancies with respect to the objectives of the engagement (see the previous section), it is necessary to collect data in a stakeholders' database (see Figure 2) containing the following information: Type of stakeholder, Name of the organisation, Address, Sectors of interest, Topic of interest among the DECISO topics, Scale of interest, Level of engagement, Contact information (Name, Family name, E-mail, Phone number).

DECISO
Stakeholders information

Type of Stakeholder

- Citizens
- Civil Society
- Policymakers
- Public Administrations and Agencies
- Private sector and Industry (consultancy, developers, services)
- Academia / Research Centres, Spin offs
- Investors

Organisation name

Address of the organisation

Topics of interest between the topics of the DECISO pilots

- Answer 1
- Answer 2

Scale of Interest of the stakeholder

- Local
- National
- European

Level of engagement

- Remain passive
- Monitor
- Advocate
- Inform
- Consult
- Negotiate
- Involve
- Collaborate
- Empower

Free Text Question

Contact information

Name of the contact person

Family Name of the contact person

E-mail Name of the contact person

Phone Number

Figure 2: DECISO Stakeholders' database

The stakeholders' Database is organised in EUSurvey. All the consortium' partners are in charge of identifying the stakeholders to engage. This activity will continue during the entire project life. This data collection is

carried out in accordance with the GDPR rules related to the management of personal data. Data are collected using the EU-Survey tool (<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/home>), which enables secure data management, and will be accessible to the consortium members to organise the project activities and in view of the DECISO community activities.

The stakeholders' identification and selection require that the project will ask the stakeholders to sign an informed consent related to the data management and an agreement for their collaboration, which will enable them to receive information and collaborate in defining business plans according to their availability and interest. The informed consent will be coherent with the "D6.3 – Informed Consent procedures" that will be released at M6 of the project but will be circulated in advance.

4. Stakeholders' engagement channels and the DECISO-DE

A DECISO community (including stakeholders at different scales) has been established mainly to facilitate effective stakeholders' engagement, discussion and contribution, and to promote the sustainability and exploitability of the outcomes. The contribution to the community is on a voluntary basis. All types of stakeholders identified in table 2 (at different scales) can contribute to discussing the specific topics addressed in the different workshops organised by the project, providing their points of view and sharing their experiences. Local and regional stakeholders can actively contribute to discussing the Operational Objectives/Specific Objectives in each pilot, and in particular, in discussing, developing and launching innovative financing schemes for CE, according to the specific topics. The national and EU level will allow exploiting these experiences at the geographical level, and producing a generalization at the topic level.

Therefore, the DECISO community will include members from the local, national and European levels. It will be organised as a community of interest that uses a digital ecosystem's main channel: the DECISO Digital Ecosystem tool (DECISO-DE). It will be an interactive hub of all the other activities organised within the project and the other channels. It is synthetically described in the next session.

The DECISO project planned the organisation of Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshops in each piloting area, and at the European level. They will enable sharing of experiences, needs and new ideas related to the CE initiatives and perspectives and the contribution to the DECISO project. These workshops will be the core activity for engaging stakeholders who can potentially be members of the DECISO community.

Local participatory workshops will involve all types of actors, promoting discussions aiming to identify the best solutions for the topics of interest within the different pilots. The workshops will make it possible to identify the stakeholders who will work within local working groups (Task 2.2 - Stakeholders' working groups and their composition) that support the promoter in defining the most suitable financing scheme and the parameters for the CE-Investments.

The DECISO project already started to establish links with the CCRI initiative and will keep in touch with sister projects / CSAs to exchange good practices (Tasks 3.6 and 3.7 – D3.4 Report on comparative analysis of pilots' experiences) and harmonise the achievements.

Journalistic articles, press releases, videos, infographics, social media posts, regional awareness campaigns and workshops in WP1, WP2 and WP5 are all activities planned within the engagement strategy, as specified within the Grant Agreement. The need for scaling up implies identifying the key regional, national and EU stakeholders, to discuss during a workshop the key points and steps of a roadmap enabling upscaling at national and European levels of the lessons learned within the DECISO pilots. The roadmap will be produced.

The effects of the all previously cited channels can be amplified using a DECISO Digital Ecosystem tool (DECISO-DE) that aims to facilitate the different stakeholders' activities, their information, collaboration and engagement at different levels and scales. DECISO-DE aims to catalyse and organise the convergence of already existing networks, communities, and projects about the CE within an online socio-technical environment that facilitates and stimulates the direct engagement of the different types of stakeholders before identified, facilitating the upscaling of outputs and outcomes.

Indeed, the digital ecosystem is part of the overall ecosystemic approach used within the DECISO project, which implies the stakeholders' engagement at different levels and different scales in the face2face, virtual and hybrid activities of the project, but also after the end of the project for exploiting the results and share experiences and the Knowledge produced by the consortium.

DECISO-DE is complementary with respect to the information provided within the website of the project (information that DECISO makes available), as DECISO-DE provides the stakeholders with an interactive environment, facilitating active engagement, open dialogue, interaction and collaboration, while the website aims to inform about the project. The Website and the DECISO-DE can be accessed by the stakeholders in a unitary way as two parts of a whole.

DECISO-DE has been configured by CNR and hosted on the CNR secure servers, based on the experience of the previous project, BIOVOICES social platform (<https://www.biovoices-platform.eu/>) and it is connected and accessible from the DECISO website (<https://www.decisoproject.eu/deciso-ecosystem/index>). It will remain active after the end of the project.

The stakeholders' engagement activities will be facilitated by the DECISO-DE, enabling them to improve as much as possible their level of engagement, even among stakeholders at different scales.

Stakeholders can play both the role of consumer and provider of resources (services, information and Knowledge). Indeed, each one can use the DECISO-DE to organise workshops, conferences, or other events in person, in a hybrid way or virtually. Indeed, the on-line registration of participants, sharing the agenda and presentations, sharing videos and images, starting the virtual conference (in streaming) that can hybridise the event in presence, sharing documents with the outcomes of the event, providing a chat for the online discussion also after the event is closed, are all functionalities that facilitate collecting information and to make them accessible during the time reducing the risk of information loss. A library of documents and financial schema produced by DECISO, but also documents of interests produced in other local areas and made available by stakeholders, can be accessed.

Differently from websites, this DECISO digital ecosystem is community-oriented and aims to facilitate the building and sharing of Knowledge and a common understanding of the CE, playing an active role in the discussion, co-creation, and sharing activities.

Summarising, the members of the DECISO-DE community may play a proactive role, reading and sharing News and managing Events, such as workshops, conferences, webinars, etc., with their Agendas, links to the online events, videos, pictures, documents, presentations and comments.

Aiming to find information, it is possible to use some filters related to the status of an activity (Upcoming, Running, Ended) or by start date, by last contribution, or alphabetically (from A to Z or from Z to A).

The [homepage of the DECISO-DE](#) is hosting a *Jump to the user guide* button, linking to the [DECISO Digital Ecosystem user guide](#), aiming to facilitate its use.

Figure 3: DECISO Digital Ecosystem

The DECISO DE usability will be improved with other filters, i.e., content grouped by one of the four DECISO pilots, to facilitate also the visualization of the activities pilot per pilot. Also, facilities to access information and documents shared within the DECISO-DE by keywords will be made available.

One webinar and a campaign of engagement within sister projects for inviting them to share also their contents and news will be carried out starting from September 2024.

5. DECISO Stakeholders' engagement plan

As already specified above, when defining the stakeholders' engagement plan, it is necessary to: provide information; capacity building to equip communities and stakeholders with an effective engagement; listen and respond to community and stakeholder concerns; include communities and stakeholders in relevant decision making-processes; developing good will and an understanding of objectives and priorities which will lead to confidence in decisions; establishing a realistic understanding of potential outcomes; and building an understanding of the decision-making process.

For this purpose, DECISO will organise:

1. working groups (organised and managed by the DECISO partners) involving stakeholders in the pilot areas for contributing to the definition of the business plans;
2. Mutual and Mobilisation Learning (MML) workshops (one in each pilot) to report, share and discuss the outcomes to 1) increase the awareness of stakeholders on the good practices that can be applied in each piloting area based on the set objectives and the ambition of the programme, 2) identify the financial supports available at local, national and European level, 3) identify the framework legislative/regulatory necessary for the success of the programme;
3. A participatory workshop will be organised at the European level (M6) by ACR+ in Brussels, involving European experts of CE and sister projects to identify and discuss good practices and opportunities

- at the European level, how they can contribute at the local level, and what kind of support can provide to the project.
4. A national participatory workshop (M8) will be organised in each piloting area to identify and discuss good practices and opportunities at the national level, how they can contribute at the local level, and what kind of support can provide to the project.
 5. Each pilot will organise a review workshop (using participatory methodologies), at M16, aiming to discuss and validate the SWOT identifying the advantages, disadvantages, capabilities, gaps and potential effects related to the ambition of the programme and the role of local actors in developing it.
 6. At M23 pilots will organise at least one review workshop (using participatory methodologies) to discuss the programmes.
 7. Dissemination includes two workshops per each pilot area, respectively within the launch of the programme, and at the end, when the selected proposals have been selected.
 8. Two Annual Conferences will be organised as a dissemination activity;
 9. For sustainability and exploitation ACR+ with the support of OV and KOYS and the other partners will organise one workshop (in Brussels) involving the local, national and EU stakeholders aiming to stimulate a trusted discussion, documenting feedback/uptake and receiving the input from potential replicators for codifying a roadmap that facilitates the replicability and supports scale-up of good solutions from DECISO.

All the previous activities will be carried out in a hybrid way, according to an ecosystemic approach, collecting, sharing, and maintaining available as much as possible experiences, information, good practices, roadmaps, etc. This approach will facilitate the mutual connection and collaboration with all the stakeholders and the CCRI community, and their exploitation and scaling up.

Many engagement activities already planned in DECISO are related to the organisation of events. For this reason, the following subsection details the steps to carry out events and to extract outcomes from them, sharing each step within the DECISO-DE strengthens the engagement impact.

6. Events (workshops, conferences, focus groups) organisation implementation and follow-up

This section aims to provide guidelines on how to organise, implement and follow up events in a coherent way in different countries and at different scales.

The general steps of developing, implementing analysing and sharing the results of an event (conference, workshop or other meetings) will be the following:

Table 3: Steps for organising, implementing, analysing and sharing the results of an event

Component	Action
Team	1. Recruit a workshop team and select a facilitator in case of the event uses a participatory methodology
Preparation	2. Identify the hot topic that you will address during the event. Formulate an abstract (and the triggering questions in case of participatory workshops).
	3. Outline the political, economic, social, scientific, and legislative context and the context of the hot topic by completing the Hot Topic Template.
	4. Select the preferred format for the event (Conference, World café workshop, Open space technology workshop, etc.).
	5. Establish the date and location of the event.

	<p>6. Share the hot topic description, date, and location of the event in a document within the DECISO partners in the common space in TEAMS (in a folder into the specific WP. For example, for workshops organised for WP2, you can share your document in a folder into the WP2 folder in TEAMS).</p> <p>7. Prepare a detailed programme for the workshop.</p> <p>8. Prepare the workshop participant-specific materials: an agenda, an informed consent form (printed and online), content documents, pictures, posters, videos, presentations, posts for social networks, leaflets, etc.. If the event is organised at the local level, all materials can be produced using the national language. It is asked to produce a summary and the agenda also in English. The final report of the event has to be both in the national language and in English, to facilitate the dissemination and exploitation of the results.</p> <p>9. Define the event within the DECISO-DE and upload any materials defined within the previous step.</p> <p>10. Identify the types of stakeholders and create a list of the specific stakeholders to involve and describe why.</p> <p>11. Set up a stakeholder involvement plan (describing the channels to contact them, how to plan the collaboration, how to recruit them and the follow-up after the event). Start two months ahead of the potential date.</p> <p>12. Send invitations and recruit participants one month ahead of the date of the workshop at the latest according to the involvement plan (by e-mail, by phone, etc.) and the CCRI community. Be sure the purpose of the workshop is clearly detailed.</p> <p>13. Sending your invitation (see the previous step) you have to: a) share the link to the DECISO DE containing the agenda and any engaging material, which provides information useful for the discussion before the event; b) ask the potential participant to get registered in the event (in the on-line DECISO-DE).</p> <p>14. Revise the participant list, and look for new names and contact stakeholders again (by telephone, e-mail or any other channel selected for the scope).</p> <p>15. Starting one month before the event share information about the event on social networks (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter) at least two times per week.</p> <p>16. When you share information about the event in the social networks (as specified in the previous step) you have to: a) share the link to the DECISO DE containing the link to the agenda and any engaging material which provides information useful for the discussion (preliminary documents, videos, etc.) before the event starting; b) ask the potential participant to get registered in the event (using the on-line DECISO-DE).</p> <p>17. Organise the logistics (book the room for the in-person participation, organise the connection for the online participants, book refreshments, etc.).</p>
During the event	<p>18. Carry out the workshop face-to-face or (hybrid) or only virtually.</p> <p>19. Create a live stream using DECISO-DE (in the event space) that enables to organise the virtual or blended events.</p> <p>20. Create a live stream using DECISO-DE (in the event space) that enables sharing the speaker's presentations online with people that cannot attend locally the event (remotely connected participants) (this requires a wide bandwidth).</p> <p>21. Create a live stream for participants from different locations that can discuss remotely. More than one streaming can be organised (this requires a wide bandwidth). This can be useful for virtual or blended events.</p>
Analysis	<p>22. Complete the Reporting Template. Evaluate the results of the event.</p>
Follow-up	<p>23. Upload presentations in the DECISO-DE (if they were not already shared during the event).</p> <p>24. Upload in the DECISO-DE pictures, videos and other materials taken and collected during the face2face event.</p> <p>25. Upload in the DECISO-DE documents elaborated after the event that are its outcomes (for example the report that synthesises the results of the event, for example, the result of a Mutual Mobilization learning workshop).</p> <p>26. Send a message or an email to all participants, to notify them that the outcomes from the event are available online.</p> <p>27. Disseminate the results (mainly within the stakeholders involved in the event and the CCRI community), using social networks and other conferences.</p> <p>28. Use the results as new inputs in the WPs of DECISO and with other communities.</p> <p>29. Ask stakeholders to continue their contribution in the online event space (in the DECISO-DE space, providing comments and discussing using the Chat).</p>

For organising any event, it is necessary to understand what the best type of event is considering the relevant features of the event. For this purpose, it is suggested to use the M2EED online tool (Biancone 2021), currently accessible at <https://www.biovoices-platform.eu/biovoicesMtool/>. It is an online tool already developed in the previous project (the BIOVOICES H2020 project). It supports the design of events. Once selected the event format, M2EED facilitates designing the event planning and configuring the agenda, based on a series of event information parameters provided by the user.

The MEED tool provides a set of functionalities to obtain a customised agenda and a set of documents related to the choices you made during the process.

In particular, the suggested format can be influenced by the type of stakeholder, and the size of the target group. The tool can be customised according to the DECISO needs, and it will be made accessible from the DECISO-DE.

In the preparation, the implementation as well as the post-event work it is necessary to analyse the event and information collected and the obtained outcomes with respect to the intended one. This means for instance that:

- The objectives of the event need to be formulated in a way that the intended outcomes are clear to participants from the beginning. This should be reflected in the event programme.
- The event is implemented and facilitated in a way that produces clear outcomes.
- Post-meeting analysis of event materials by the organising partner, including drafting of an Event Report. This includes documentation of discussions and their analysis and conclusions.
- Follow-up with participants. It is recommended to follow up with participants by sending them the Report, link to documents, presentations, pictures and link to the online event, as well as other information material (including them in the DECISO-DE). The outcomes of the event will include:
- The composition of participants (type of stakeholders, number of participants segregated by gender)
- Outcomes which impact the project objectives.

Table 4 gives the template of the DECISO event report.

Table 4: template for the DECISO event report

DECISO: : EVENT REPORT TEMPLATE	
TITLE OF THE EVENT	...
DATE OF THE EVENT	...
TYPE OF EVENT (CONFERENCE, WORLD CAFÈ, ETC.)	...
MODALITY (VIRTUAL, HYBRID)	...
LOCATION (IF HYBRID INDICATE ALSO THE LINK TO THE DECISO-DE EVENT)	...
NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (SEGREGATED PER GENDER)	...
GENERAL OBJECTIVES OF THE EVENT	...
TYPE OF STAKEHOLDER	...
VALUE-BASED MOTIVATIONS FOR EACH TYPE OF STAKEHOLDER TO ATTEND THE EVENT	...
HOW THE OUTCOMES PROVIDE AN ANSWER TO THE EXPECTANCIES	...
WHAT IS THE ROLE THAT THE DIFFERENT STAKEHOLDERS CAN PLAY WITHIN DECISO	...
WHAT IS THE LEVEL OF ENGAGEMENT OF EACH STAKEHOLDER	...
DETAIL NEXT ACTIVITIES IF PLANNED	...
PICTURES OF THE EVENT	...
LINK TO THE EVENT IN THE DECISO-DE	...
GENERAL COMMENTS AND LESSONS LEARNED	...

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8. Annex I - Invitation letter

To: XXXX

From: YYYY

Object: Invitation to Join the DECISO database of stakeholders

Dear **Name and Family name of the stakeholder**,

“DECISO- DEvelopers of Circular SOLutions” is an Horizon Europe project (Grant agreement ID: 101082232) funded by the European Commission.

DECISO aims to support the delivery of services to induce investments projects for developing Circular Economy at local and regional scales in the following regions: Hamburg. Northwest Germany, West Macedonia, Alentejo. This is in line with implementing the European Green Deal and the EU circular economy action plan. DECISO will accompany the actions aiming to provide assistance for promoters in the development of financial schemes/programs for projects on Circular Economy, based on the concept of Circular Economy Ecosystem (CEE), which implies mobilizing local stakeholders and, when necessary, citizens, and scaling up the results from the local, to the national and European levels.

We send you some materials such as the flyer and the leaflet about the DECISO project jointly with this letter. The project started in 2022 and it is now in the phase of the core activity period with the implementation of many workshops and the building of the DECISO stakeholders' community. For this purpose, we are inviting you to join the DECISO stakeholders' community and to agree that your organisation and you will be included in the database of stakeholders. This will enable you to receive information on the activities carried out and be invited to participate and contribute to them on a voluntary basis.

Kind Regards

Date, **xxxx**

Name, Family name and Email of the partner who is sending the invitation letter

Signature

